

The Effect of Employee Engagement and Work Environment on Teacher Performance Mediated by Work Discipline at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah in Ciledug District, Tangerang City

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Abstract:- This study aims to analyze the effect of employee engagement and work environment on teacher performance mediated by work discipline at MI in Ciledug District, Tangerang City. All MI teachers in Ciledug District, Tangerang City, totaling 193 people from six different schools as the population. The sampling technique was proportional stratified random sampling, it was found that 130 people were selected as samples through the Slovin formula. Data was taken by questionnaire and then analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling Partial Least Square (SEMPLS). The final results shown from the research are (1) Employee engagement has a significant indirect effect on teacher performance, (2) Work environment has a significant indirect effect on teacher performance, (3) Employee engagement and work environment have a significant positive effect on work discipline, (4) Employee attachment and work discipline have a significant positive effect on teacher performance, but the work environment has no significant effect on teacher performance.

Keywords:- Employee Engagement, Work Environment, Work Discipline, Teacher Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teachers must give their thoughts and energy to teach and provide direction, training, assessment, and evaluation to students. Therefore, teachers are a fundamental asset for schools, because, without teachers, school activities will not occur. Teachers function actively when planning, implementing, and evaluating the goals to be achieved by the school. Each school is required to direct teachers and education personnel to utilize effective and efficient resources. A capable teacher owned by the school certainly contributes its advantages. This condition can be seen if the teacher can carry out the various obligations given.

The main element in determining the quality of education is teacher performance. Concerning teacher performance, the form of integrity is all teacher activities in the teaching and learning process. The quality of educational outcomes is required by the quality of teacher performance

because the teacher is a person who is directly related to students.

Factors that affect the success of the performance shown by the teacher is the work environment. Work productivity is mainly supported by the work environment. Productive employees are a picture of an advanced organization, where it departs from small things that have a big impact, namely the employee's work environment. The work environment can be said to be good if individuals who are in that environment can feel safe, comfortable and can carry out their activities optimally.

Teacher performance can also be affected by teacher attachment. Teacher attachment is the emotional attachment that teachers have to the school. Teachers are aware that their vision and mission are in line with the school.

Therefore, a close commitment to the school's vision and mission, as well as concern for the obligations that are the responsibility of the teacher, will be owned by the teacher. So that the teacher does his job happily and does not consider it a burden. Teachers who work happily will provide benefits to the school, namely increasing work productivity which will ultimately improve performance.

Interviews were conducted with the Madrasah Superintendent of Ciledug district, Mr. Rusli, S.Ag, M.Pd, which gave the result that MI teachers must take care of each other and work together with colleagues to build an optimal work environment. It was also stated that the performance of MI teachers in Ciledug District, Tangerang City, had not yet met the expectations of the organization.

The target of achieving teacher performance in terms of understanding and compiling learning tools with the 2017 to 2019 school year has not yet reached 100%, with the highest percentage value of 71% and the lowest percentage of 60%.

There have been many studies related to the performance of previous researchers. Factors that affect employee performance are: work environment Badrianto & Ekhsan [1]; Hafeez I., Yingjun, Hafeez S., Mansoor & Rehman [2]; Firmansyah, Maupa, Taba & Hardiyono [3],

discipline (Wahyudi [4]; Sari & Gundo [5]; Rahayu & Ajimat [6]), employee engagement (Sabu V.G & Manoj M. [7]; Eka & Anik [8]; Suryanthini, Landra & Agung, [9]).

From the previous study above, the researcher conducted a pre-survey with respondents to 31 MI teachers in Ciledug District, Tangerang City. The pre-survey shows that there are variables of employee attachment, discipline, and work environment with a large number of respondents. The first variable factor, employee attachment is a variable that must be considered by the organization because success in all aspects of the organization is directly influenced by employee attachment. Employee engagement arises from personal intentions that are in line with the direction and values of the organization. Employees who have attachments then become more useful, harmonious, and focused on personal and organizational development.

When employees participate effectively in the organization, they will not only work to earn money but will take into account how much participation the organization has and want to move forward with the group. The substance of employee attachment raises the impetus for employees to be more responsible for work assignments.

Work discipline is also the main thing that must be considered and should not be ignored. There are various positive arguments why work discipline must be maintained. Minimize the difficulties caused by undisciplined actions. For example, work delays and attendance often hinder the productivity of employees and their teams.

When discipline is implemented consistently and fairly, it can maintain organizational standards, which in turn can strengthen the rules that have been determined by the organization and is capable of elevating organizational culture and maintaining organizational standards.

The work environment plays a direct role in the psychology of each employee so that they can carry out their activities in a healthy, safe, and comfortable manner for the sake of increasing individual productivity.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Employee Engagement

Kahn (1990) firstly describes employee attachment, a condition in which the organization identifies itself with its work. Bringing positive attitude from employees towards the organization and the values of the organization. Engaged employees can fully involve sensitivity, physically and emotionally in their work, they are not even aware that time is running which has the potential to improve performance to achieve organizational benefits, Robinson, Perryman, & Hayday [10].

According to Kruse [11] employee engagement is a form of employee's emotional commitment to the organization with the aim that employees genuinely care about their work and the company. Employees do not work

for wages even for promotions but work for and on behalf of the organization's goals.

As a form of emotional commitment of employees to the organization with the aim of employees properly caring for the job and the company. Employees do not work for wages even for promotions but work for and on behalf of the organization's goals.

Another view assumes employee engagement as opposed to burnout. Schaufeli & Bakker [12] assume that burnout represents a negative pole and engagement as a positive pole, so that engagement and burnout embody two opposite poles of the continuum regarding work-related well-being.

B. Work Environment

Sedarmayanti [13], the work environment is the entire facility and infrastructure found around the employee, the area a person learns, work patterns, and work arrangements both in terms of individuals and teams or groups. An environment where employees do their work every day, Siagian [14].

Sutrisno [15] the work environment is the state of the employee while doing the job that will motivate the implementation of the work in terms of the overall work facilities and infrastructure. Circumstances, namely the work location, facilities, lighting, cleanliness, tranquility, and the relationship between employees.

C. Work Discipline

Work discipline is a tool used by managers in dealing with employees for the sake of their willingness to change a behavior to gain individual awareness in complying with all the rules and social norms that apply in the organization Rivai [16]. Another view, work discipline does not arise by itself because in essence discipline is how to raise employee awareness to continue to carry out the obligations given, Harlie [17].

D. Teacher Performance

Achievement of the work of employees in carrying out their obligations and responsibilities to them both in quality and quantity, Mangkunegara [18]. Same with that Rivai [16] Performance is defined as real behavior issued by each individual for work performance according to his obligations and responsibilities in the organization.

Teacher performance has certain specifications, one of which is the competency that every teacher needs to have is a benchmark for teacher performance. In addition, all teacher activities in the learning process become a barometer of the integrity of teacher performance.

The main competencies of teachers are planning, implementing and leading, assessing, and fostering relationships with children, all of which are packaged in the teaching and learning process.

E. Conceptual Framework

Departing from what has been described previously, this research follows the line of thought as shown in Figure 1 below.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

The formulation of the hypothesis is as follows:

- H1: Employee engagement affects work discipline.
- H2: The work environment affects work discipline.
- H3: Work discipline affects teacher performance.
- H4: Employee engagement affects teacher performance.
- H5: The work environment affects teacher performance.
- H6: Employee engagement affects teacher performance through work discipline.
- H7: The work environment affects teacher performance through work discipline.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research study is a cause-and-effect study, by analyzing the hypothesis about the effect of one or more variables X on variable Y. The research uses a quantitative approach through literature study and measurement of the results using primary data on the distribution of questionnaires and the assessment of the variable scale using the Likert scale.

In addition, to complement relevant data and complement each other, this research study uses secondary data in the form of teacher performance reports for 2019-2021 obtained from supervisors of Madrasah Ibtidaiyah throughout Ciledug District, Tangerang City. The data obtained were

analyzed using validity and reliability testing activities. The quantitative analysis method uses statistical analysis. The results are presented and interpreted, and the last is to write a conclusion and suggestions.

All MI teachers in Ciledug District, Tangerang City, totaling 193 people from six different schools as the population. By using the Slovin formula, the smallest sample size of this study was determined by = 5% (95% confidence level), so that the smallest number of samples (n) was 130.1855 rounded down the number of respondents who were used as a sample of 130 teachers who teach at MI in Ciledug districts. The number of samples as many as 130 has met the minimum sample requirements for SEMPLS analysis, which is ten times the maximum number of structural paths according to the ten times rule formula proposed by Barclay, Higgins, dan Thompson ([19]).

Data were collected through literature study, interviews, and questionnaires. Furthermore, it was analyzed descriptively to the respondents and their variables. Data analysis method with Partial Least Square (PLS).

The assessment study of the PLS model consists of two stages, namely the assessment of the outer model and the inner model.

Fig. 2. Conceptual Framework

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Respondent's Description

Female respondents were dominated by 96 people (74%) and 34 men (26%). Age characteristics were dominated by the age of 31-50 years by 76 respondents (58%) then age >30 years by 54 respondents (42%) and none over 50 years (0%). A total of 64 people (49%) or >10 years are dominant, 26 respondents have worked > 2 - 5 years (20%), 23 respondents have worked > 5-10 years (18%) and have worked < 2 years are 17 respondents (13%). Based on the level of education, it is dominated by 124 S1 graduates (95%) and 6 S2 graduates (5%).

B. Variable Description

The research variables are employee attachment (X1), work environment (X2), work discipline (Z), and teacher performance (Y). In employee engagement (X1), the dimensions of enthusiasm, dedication, and absorption consist of 10 statements. A total of 66.5 people said they tend to strongly agree that they are enthusiastic to work every time they work. Meanwhile, the average dedication dimension of respondents tends to agree with an average of 63.5. Likewise, with the absorption dimension, respondents agreed to the absorption with an average of 80.

The work environment (X2) has dimensions of the physical and non-physical work environment consisting of 5 statements. Most of the respondents, 80.5, stated that they tend to agree that the dimensions of the physical work environment help the work carried out. Likewise, with the dimensions of the non-physical work environment on average, 64.7 agreed.

Work discipline (Z) has dimensions of effective time measurement, responsibility in work and assignments and absenteeism consists of 10 statements. In the dimension of effective time measurement, most of the respondents 83.5 stated that they tend to agree that there is effective time measurement. Likewise, on the dimensions of responsibility

in work and assignments, respondents tend to agree with an average value of 68. The absenteeism dimension of respondents tends to agree with the absentee dimension with an average of 74.5.

Teacher performance (Y) has dimensions of planning the learning process, implementing the learning process, assessing learning outcomes, and supervising the learning process, consisting of 15 statements. With an average number of 89.00 respondents tend to agree to the dimensions of planning the learning process. Likewise, for the dimensions of implementing the learning process respondents tend to agree with an average number of 66.00. In line with the two dimensions above, the dimension of assessing the learning outcomes of respondents also tends to agree with an average number of 80.00. Not much different from the dimensions of assessing learning outcomes, the dimensions of respondents tend to agree to the dimensions of carrying out the learning process with an average of 4.44.

C. Validity Test

Testing the convergent validity of an instrument is met if the loading factor value is above 0.5. Exposure to convergent validity testing as below:

Table 1 Average Variance Extracted Score (Ave)

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Employee Engagement	0,520
Environment	0,620
Work Discipline	0,538
Teacher Performance	0,611

Convergent validity test in PLS is done by measuring the reflective indicators assessed based on the loading factor. The higher the loading factor value, the more important the role of loading in translating the factor matrix is. TABLE I shows the results of the measurement model calculation with SmartPLS that the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) score of all variables has a score > 0.50. This shows that the indicator variable is declared valid and fixed.

Table 2 Cross Loading Value After Modification

	Employee Engagement	Work Environment	Teacher Performance	Work Discipline
EE.1.1	0,630	0,384	0,319	0,322
EE.1.2	0,808	0,475	0,547	0,548
EE.1.3	0,778	0,531	0,516	0,568
EE.1.4	0,770	0,516	0,490	0,447
EE.2.1	0,772	0,500	0,619	0,560
EE.2.2	0,722	0,566	0,556	0,586
EE.2.3	0,678	0,476	0,510	0,500
EE.2.4	0,612	0,542	0,563	0,530
EE.3.1	0,743	0,527	0,572	0,589

	Employee Engagement	Work Environment	Teacher Performance	Work Discipline
EE.3.2	0,669	0,431	0,501	0,533
WE.1.2	0,619	0,803	0,602	0,670
WE.2.1	0,587	0,829	0,657	0,627
WE.2.2	0,504	0,889	0,629	0,677
WE.2.3	0,528	0,885	0,656	0,682
TP.1.2	0,600	0,595	0,825	0,738
TP.1.3	0,523	0,578	0,760	0,670
TP.1.4	0,458	0,569	0,734	0,670
TP.2.1	0,553	0,527	0,689	0,593
TP.2.2	0,567	0,541	0,762	0,627
TP.2.3	0,696	0,622	0,876	0,725
TP.3.1	0,558	0,628	0,809	0,661
TP.3.2	0,552	0,667	0,825	0,746
TP.3.3	0,585	0,563	0,726	0,641
TP.4.1	0,597	0,632	0,840	0,685
TP.4.2	0,556	0,597	0,801	0,681
TP.4.3	0,628	0,656	0,853	0,707
TP.4.4	0,633	0,656	0,862	0,692
WD.1.1	0,667	0,645	0,731	0,826
WD.1.2	0,528	0,526	0,624	0,768
WD.2.1	0,682	0,769	0,800	0,852
WD.2.2	0,518	0,613	0,602	0,714
WD.2.3	0,612	0,593	0,642	0,765
WD.2.4	0,482	0,558	0,697	0,737
WD.3.1	0,439	0,456	0,455	0,664
WD.3.2	0,416	0,564	0,555	0,634
WD.3.3	0,423	0,365	0,435	0,512
WD.3.4	0,488	0,696	0,672	0,799

After modifications were made to the work environment construct indicator X2.1.1 and teacher performance constructs indicator Y.1.1, all indicators have shown a cross-loading value that is greater than the other constructs so that they are declared valid.

D. Reliability Test

Table 3 Reliability Test

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
EE	0,896	0,915
WE	0,833	0,887
TP	0,949	0,956
WD	0,901	0,919

Cronbach's Alpha and composite reliability values on X1, X2, Y and Z > 0.7 and the composite reliability score > 0.8. This value has exceeded the respective standards, namely > 0.6 and > 0.7, this shows that the consistency of the instrument used is high, thus X1, X2, Y, and Z are said to be reliable.

E. R-square (R²) Value

TABLE IV. R-SQUARE VALUE

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
TP	0,767	0,761
WD	0,698	0,693

The adjusted R square value is as follows:

- The value of X1 is 0.761, this shows that the model with the teacher performance variable has a predictive power at a strong level. In conclusion, 76.1% of the variance of teacher performance variables can be explained by the variables of employee attachment, work environment, and work discipline.
- The Z value is 0.693, this shows that the model with the work discipline variable has a predictive power at a moderate level. In conclusion, 69.3% of the variance of the work discipline variable can be explained by the work attachment and work environment variables.

F. Q-Square Analysis

In addition to the R Square value, the measurement of the inner model is also measured using the predictive relevance value (Q²) where the values obtained are 0.02 (small), 0.15 (medium), and 0.35 (large). The formula used to obtain predictive values relevance (Q²):

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q^2 &= 1 - (R^2_1)(1 - R^2_n) \\
 &= 1 - (1-0,761)(1-0,693) \\
 &= 1 - (0,239)(0,307) \\
 &= 1 - 0,073 \\
 &= 0,926 \\
 &= 92,6\%
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

The results of the Q² calculation show that the predictive relevance value in the structural model in this study is > 0. This means that it shows evidence that the observed values have been reconstructed properly, therefore the model has a predictive relevance of 92.6%, in conclusion, the model can explain events related to variables researched. So, the model can be said to have a very good predictive value for hypothesis testing.

G. The goodness of Fit Value

The goodness of Fit Value:

$$\begin{aligned}
 GoF &= \sqrt{AVE \times R^2} \\
 &= \sqrt{0.572 \times 0.761} \\
 &= 0,87
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2}$$

The results of the Goodness of Fit calculation show the results of 0.87 which means that the combined result between the outer model and the inner model is large.

H. Research Variable Dimension Test

Fig. 3. Bootstrapping Measurement Model Calculation Results

- Explanation of Figure 3 above, namely:
- The dominant dimension influencing employee attachment variable is enthusiasm (X1.1) of 77,216. The most dominant indicator influencing employee attachment variable is in item X1.3.1 of 40.133. The most dominant indicator influencing the work environment variable is in item X2.2.3 of 43.304.
 - The dimension with the greatest contribution in shaping the work environment variable is the non-physical work environment (X2.2) of 129,778. The dominant indicator affecting the work discipline variable is in point Z.1.1 of 48.167.
 - The dimension that has the biggest contribution in shaping the work discipline variable is responsibility in work and duties (Z.2) of 73,427. The dominant indicator influencing the teacher's performance variable is found in item Y.1.2 of 48.961.
 - The dimension that has the biggest contribution in shaping the performance of work teachers is supervising the learning process (Y.4) of 49,769.

I. Hypothesis test

	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values	Description
EE -> TP	0,183	0,195	0,073	2,500	0,013	Positive significant
EE -> WD	0,331	0,341	0,084	3,921	0,000	Positive significant
WE -> TP	0,153	0,155	0,101	1,514	0,131	not significant
WE -> WD	0,572	0,564	0,094	6,083	0,000	Positive significant
DK -> K	0,603	0,587	0,106	5,693	0,000	Positive significant

TABLE V. PATH COEFFICIENT TEST RESULTS

The t-count value of 1.975 is the basis for making decisions, the hypothesis is accepted if the T-statistic > 1.975, and the hypothesis is rejected if the T-statistic < 1.975. For the

significance value at P-value, if P-value < 0.05 then the hypothesis is accepted and if P-value > 0.05 then the hypothesis is rejected.

TABLE VI. SPECIFIC INDIRECT EFFECT RESULT

	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values
EE -> WD -> TP	0,199	0,199	0,060	3,332	0,001
WE -> WD -> TP	0,345	0,331	0,082	4,211	0,000

TABLE VII. TOTAL EFFECT RESULT

	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values
WD -> TP	0,603	0,587	0,106	5,693	0,000
EE -> WD	0,331	0,341	0,084	3,921	0,000
EE -> TP	0,383	0,394	0,091	4,214	0,000
WE -> WD	0,572	0,564	0,094	6,083	0,000
WE -> TP	0,498	0,487	0,104	4,795	0,000

First Hypothesis Analysis: Employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on work discipline. This finding explains the path coefficient obtained is 0.331 with a T-

Statistic of 3.921 > T table 1.975 and p values of 0.000 < 0.05, so H1 is accepted, substantively it can be explained that employees who have an engagement to their work will be

more disciplined towards their work in harmony with previous research by Pratiwi Triasti and Charles Bohlen Purba [20].

Second Hypothesis Analysis: The work environment has a positive and significant effect on work discipline. This finding explains that the path coefficient obtained is 0.572 with a T-Statistic of 6.083 > T table of 1.975 and a p-value of 0.000 < 0.05, thus H2 is accepted. Substantively, it can be explained that the better the work environment received by the workforce, the higher the influence on work discipline. This is in line with the research of Badrianto & Ekhsan [1].

Third Hypothesis Analysis: Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. This finding explains that the path coefficient obtained is 0.603 with a T-Statistic of 5.693 > T table of 1.975 and a p-value of 0.000 < 0.05, thus H3 is accepted. In conclusion, work discipline that is grown by superiors to their subordinates can spur a sense of responsibility towards work because the workforce is aware of their obligations. This is similar in research by Rahayu & Ajimat [6] and Wahyudi [21].

Fourth Hypothesis Analysis: Employee attachment has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. This finding explains that the path coefficient obtained is 0.183 with a T-Statistic of 2.500 > T table 1.975 and p values of 0.013 < 0.05, thus H4 is accepted, in line with previous research Sabu V.G & Manoj M., [7] and Eka Febrial dan Anik Hermaningsih [8].

Fifth Hypothesis Analysis: The work environment has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. This finding explains that the path coefficient obtained is 0.153 with a T-Statistic of 1.514 < T table of 1.975 and a p-value of 0.131 > 0.05, thus H5 is rejected. In line with previous research by Miftahul Ainun Naím Basori, Wawan Prahawan and Daenulhay [22] and Lindu Prabowo [23].

Sixth Hypothesis Analysis: Employee Attachment has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance through work discipline. This finding explains that the path coefficient obtained is 0.199 with a T-Statistic of 3.332 > T table of 1.975 and a p-value of 0.001 < 0.05, thus H6 is accepted. It can be concluded that employee attachment has a significant effect on teacher performance through work discipline, in line with previous research Baron and Kenny [24], Pratiwi Triasti and Charles Bohlen Purba [20].

Seventh Hypothesis Analysis: The work environment has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance through work discipline. This finding explains the path coefficient obtained by 0.345 with T-Statistic 4.211 > T table 1.975 and P values of 0.000 < 0.05, thus H7 is accepted. It can be concluded that the work environment has a significant effect on teacher performance through work discipline, in line with research Baron and Kenny [24], Elok Mahmud Putri, Vivin Maharani Ekowati, Achmad Sani Supriyanto, and Zaim Mukaffi [25] also Aidil Syahrin [26].

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

A. conclusions

- Employee attachment has a positive and significant effect on work discipline. Focus while working is very dominant in influencing employee attachment. This means that employees who have an attachment to their work become more and more passionate about their work then it motivates the emergence of self-discipline in employees in the work they do.
- The work environment has a positive and significant effect on work discipline. Communication between superiors in the work environment goes well, very dominantly affects the work environment, the better the non-physical work environment accepted by employees, so it has a stronger impact on the discipline.
- Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. Obeying the SOPs that have been regulated, making teachers more concerned about their obligations.
- Employee engagement has a significant effect on teacher performance. This means that it illustrates the engagement of MI teachers in the Ciledug district is high. High engagement makes teachers want to do assignments and work targets from school.
- The work environment in MI in Ciledug does not significantly affect teacher performance.
- Employee engagement has a significant effect on teacher performance through work discipline. From the findings that work discipline plays a significant role as a mediator to improve teacher performance. The higher employee engagement will bring up work discipline that can improve performance.
- The work environment has a significant effect on teacher performance through work discipline. From the findings that the work environment does not have a significant effect on performance, but if work discipline is added as a mediation, it produces a significant effect in improving teacher performance. This proves that discipline can act as a mediating variable to improve teacher performance.

B. Suggestions

- Attempting to massively improve teacher performance with work discipline, one of which is supported in fixed procedures and must be carried out by teachers. Build positive behavior and increase morale in employees to foster high performance.
- Aim to improve work discipline, one of which is full attention to the work environment, especially in the non-physical work environment. Maintaining healthy communication in the school environment can lead to good social attitudes.
- Strive to create a safe, comfortable, and family atmosphere in the school work environment. The role of teachers and leaders contributes directly to the goal of creating a comfortable and pleasant work atmosphere.
- Actions to maintain and improve the work environment, one of which is by building good relationships between employees and a conducive workspace, will cause teacher performance to increase due to the work spirit that arises within oneself to work well.

- For further researchers, they can review with an in-depth study related to the problems in this research so that clearer data and information are obtained. It is hoped that future research will be supported by the addition of a large population and new variables to reach the level of perfection, be useful and synergize with the results of this research study.

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